

alcohol it melted at 53-55°. It was distilled under reduced pressure and the distillate crystallised thrice from alcohol, when colourless needles were obtained (0.6 g.), m.p. 60-61°; there being no depression on admixture with a sample of pure palmitic acid. (Found: C, 74.9; H, 12.7. $C_{16}H_{32}O_2$ requires C, 75.0; H, 12.5 per cent). The aqueous filtrate showed the presence of oxalic acid.

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On Anacardic Acid. Part II. The Constitution of Tetrahydroanacardic Acid.

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Another line of investigation which threw more light on the constitution of anacardic acid was based on its behaviour on heating. On heating the acid in an atmosphere of nitrogen to 230° and distilling the product, there was obtained besides undistillable resin, an oil boiling at 215.20°/14mm. in an yield of approximately 25%. The same product was obtained in an yield of 50% when anacardic acid was distilled in *vacuo*. This oil, which is referred to as anacardol, was found by its analysis, behaviour and catalytic reduction to be the simple decarboxylated product of anacardic acid, standing in the same relationship to it as phenol to salicylic acid. It was observed that, once the carboxyl group became eliminated from anacardic acid, the hydroxyl group became easily reactive, but here again it was found to be more advantageous to study it in the saturated product.

Titration against bromine revealed the presence of two double bonds and on catalytic reduction four atoms of hydrogen were quickly taken up (*cf.* Part I) and the same compound was obtained in good yield, when tetrahydroanacardic acid was distilled under reduced pressure. It was found, however, that if tetrahydroanacardic acid is first decarboxylated by prolonged heating at 200-220° at ordinary pressure it gives besides tetrahydroanacardol, about 26% of another product as needles, almost insoluble in alcohol and melting at 49°.

By treatment with alcoholic potash for about 4 hours, it gave a mixture of tetrahydroanacardic acid and tetrahydroanacardol, the components being easily separated by suitable means. This substance, therefore, is tetrahydroanacardyl tetrahydroanacardate and its formation is analogous to the formation of salol by the action of heat on salicylic acid.

Tetrahydroanacardol easily gives crystalline acetyl, benzoyl and phenylurethane derivatives. It was found that distillation under reduced pressure of acetyltetrahydroanacardic acid results in a product melting at 42° , which is found to be the same as tetrahydroanacardyl acetate.

As is the case with other phenols having long fatty side-chains, tetrahydroanacardol gives a solid sodium derivative when rubbed with dilute caustic soda, insoluble in water but soluble in alcohol. It is oxidised by potassium permanganate in acetone solution more easily than tetrahydroanacardic acid with the formation of oxalic and palmitic acids.

The constitution of tetrahydroanacardic acid follows from that of tetrahydroanacardol. The phenolic character of the latter substance is evidenced by its formation from an *o*-phenolic acid by smooth decarboxylation, by the Liebermann's colour reaction, and by the formation of a sodium derivative and of phenols of lower molecular weight by its distillation at ordinary pressure. Since oxidation with potassium permanganate in acetone solution yields palmitic acid, tetrahydroanacardol can be inferred to contain a straight normal side-chain of 15 carbon atoms in its molecule. It is a well known fact observed in the case of saturated fatty aromatic substances that the ring system is easily oxidised with the formation of fatty acids containing one carbon atom more than the side-chain, which remains intact, this carbon atom being derived from the ring. (*cf.* hydrourushiol, hydrolacol, Majima, *Ber.*, 1922, 55, 172).

Tetrahydroanacardol ($C_{21}H_{36}O$) could, therefore, be written as $OH \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot C_{15}H_{31}$ (n), and since the phenols obtained by the distillation of anacardol under ordinary pressure give salicylic acid by fusion with potash, the side-chain must be in the *ortho* position to the hydroxyl group. Tetrahydroanacardol, therefore, has the structure (I).

As tetrahydroanacardic acid gives the violet colour reaction with ferric chloride the carboxyl group in the acid must be either in the *ortho*-position to the hydroxyl and attached to the benzene nucleus or attached to the long pentadecyl side-chain *i.e.* the tetrahydroanacardic acid is either (II) or (III).

If the acid has structure (III), oxidation should lead to the formation of a dicarboxylic acid containing 17 carbon atoms in analogy with the final oxidation products of chaulmoogric and hydnocarpic acids, which are dicarboxylic acids containing one carbon atom more than their respective side-chains (Power and Barrowcliff, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 557). Tetrahydroanacardic acid gives, however, the monocarboxylic palmitic acid, the carboxyl being evidently formed from the ring carbon atom, the benzene ring being completely ruptured in the process. It follows, therefore, that the carboxyl group of tetrahydroanacardic acid is attached to the benzene nucleus and consequently the acid has the structure (II). The smooth decarboxylation of the acid can be taken as a further evidence of the carboxyl group being attached to the benzene ring, as this appears to be a property common to all the substituted salicylic acids.

It is of interest to note in this connection that from several trees of the *Anacardiaceæ* family, catechol derivatives containing normal side-chains of 15 or 17 carbon atoms have been isolated (Majima and co-workers, *Ber.*, 1922, 55, 172; Pillay and Siddiqui, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 517), so that this kind of fatty aromatic structure seems to be favoured by the *Anacardiaceæ* family of plants.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Action of heat on anacardic acid: Formation of anacardol.—On heating anacardic acid in an atmosphere of nitrogen on the oil-bath, visible evolution of gas above 175° was observed which became quite brisk at 200°. The gas was found to be carbon dioxide. Water too was given off at about this temperature. The residue of brown oil boiled mostly at 215-220° /14 mm. in an yield of about 25%. An yield of about 50% of the same product was obtained by distilling the anacardic acid under reduced pressure. About half of the anacardic acid taken resinified in the distilling flask to a hard glassy solid insoluble in all the organic solvents and only barely acted on even by boiling nitric acid. The anacardol thus obtained has

the following properties: $d_{30}^{20} = 0.9399$; $n_D^{20} = 1.5107$. The substance gives a yellowish green colouration by Leibermann's test for phenols, but is quite insoluble in ordinary caustic soda and does not give any colouration with ferric chloride. It was found to be soluble in exceedingly dilute caustic soda, to a minute degree, much more if about 25% of alcohol was added to it. (Found: C, 84.3; H, 10.6. $C_{21}H_{32}O$ requires C, 84.0; H, 10.7 per cent).

Anacardol (0.584 g.) titrated in ice-cold chloroform solution decolourised 0.58 g. of bromine (two double bonds require 0.62 g. Br). The product was not obtained crystalline.

Catalytic hydrogenation of anacardol: Formation of tetrahydroanacardol.—Anacardol (1.925 g.) was hydrogenated in alcoholic solution using palladised charcoal as catalyst. It was very quickly hydrogenated absorbing 298 c.c. of H at N. T. P. (2 H₂ require 286 c.c.). Alcohol was distilled off and the product distilled under reduced pressure. The distillate solidified and was crystallised from petroleum ether, m. p. 53-54°. It is very soluble in all the common organic solvents. (Found: C, 83.0; H, 11.7. $C_{21}H_{36}O$ requires C, 82.9; H, 11.8 per cent).

Tetrahydroanacardic acid (1.0 g.) was distilled under reduced pressure, and the product (0.7 g.) which solidified on cooling, was crystallised from petroleum ether, m. p. 54°; the melting point was not lowered by admixture with tetrahydroanacardol obtained by the hydrogenation of anacardol.

The acetyl derivative.—Tetrahydroanacardol (0.2 g.) was boiled with acetic anhydride (1 c.c.) and a drop of pyridine for 2 hours, evaporated on the water-bath and distilled under reduced pressure. The solid distillate was crystallised by cooling an alcoholic solution in ice as needles, m. p. 42°. (Found: C, 79.9; H, 10.9. $C_{23}H_{38}O_2$ requires C, 79.8; H, 11.0 per cent). The same product was also obtained by the distillation under reduced pressure of acetyl tetrahydroanacardic acid.

The benzoyl derivative.—Tetrahydroanacardol (0.3 g.) was heated on the water-bath with an excess of benzoyl chloride for 2 hours, the excess was decomposed with methanol, the product evacuated at 100° for some time, and then the residue distilled under reduced pressure. The distillate, which solidified, was crystallised from hot alcohol as palm-leaf like needles, m. p. 54°. (Found: C, 82.1; H, 9.5. $C_{28}H_{40}O_2$ requires C, 82.3; H, 9.8 per cent).

The phenylcarbamate.—Tetrahydroanacardol (0.2 g.) in petroleum ether (2 c.c.) was treated with phenyl isocyanate (0.15 g.) and kept overnight. It solidified to a white solid which was filtered, washed with petrol and crystallised from alcohol as rosettes of silky white needles, m. p. 79-80°. (Found: N, 3.7. $C_{28}H_{40}O_2N$ requires N, 3.3 per cent).

Oxidation of tetrahydroanacardol: Isolation of palmitic and oxalic acids.—Tetrahydroanacardol (2 g.) dissolved in acetone (70 c.c.) and water (20 c.c.) was oxidised with a solution of potassium permanganate (6 g.) in acetone (80 c.c.) and water (20 c.c.). The reaction mixture became warm and the permanganate was quickly discoloured. It was filtered and worked up as in the oxidation of the acid; it gave besides oxalic acid, 0.8 g. of a fatty acid, m. p. 51-53°. When distilled under reduced pressure and crystallised thrice from alcohol 0.25 g. of an acid was obtained melting at 60-61°, the m. p. was not lowered by admixture with a sample of pure palmitic acid.

Distillation of anacardol under ordinary pressure.—Anacardol (15 g.) was twice distilled under ordinary pressure. Inflammable gases were evolved and the distillate which had a strong phenolic odour was separated by means of caustic soda dissolved in 15% alcohol and shaking with ether into (a) phenols (3 g.) and (b) non-phenols (7 g.). The latter when distilled over sodium gave what appeared to be hydrocarbons, but with a long range of boiling point. (Found: C, 86.2; H, 13.4 per cent).

(a) *Phenols.*—On fractionation, the boiling point of the phenols went on rising from about 200—350°. The first drop gave a violet colour with aqueous ferric chloride.

Potash fusion of phenols.—The phenols (2 g.) were fused with potash (20 g.) and water (4 c.c.) in a nickel crucible. An insoluble sodium salt seemed to be formed which quickly went into solution at about 300°. It was cooled, acidified, extracted with ether and separated by means of sodium bicarbonate into acids and phenols. The acid residue, when taken up with hot water and the water driven out in the desiccator, gave a partially crystalline residue, which was crystallised from hot water as needles (12 mg.) melting at 155.56°. It gives a violet colouration with ferric chloride. The melting point was not lowered by admixture with a sample of salicylic acid. The phenolic fraction (0.3 g.) gave a violet colouration with aqueous ferric chloride and gave with bromine water a bromide, which

crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles melting at 93° and was found to be tribromophenol by mixed melting point.

Action of heat on tetrahydroanacardic acid.—Tetrahydroanacardic acid (2.003 g.) was heated in a current of nitrogen in an oil-bath, and the outgoing gases estimated for carbon dioxide and water. Bubbles of gas began forming at about 195° and the effervescence was quite brisk at 225° . It was heated to 235° . The ebullition stopped in 15 minutes but the heating was continued for another 15 minutes. The substance gave 0.0343 g. of water and 0.1927 g. of carbon dioxide (9.6%; 1 mol. of CO_2 requires 12.6%). The residue was crystallised from alcohol by cooling in ice when 0.6 g. of colourless needles was obtained. This product was almost insoluble in alcohol and melted at 49° . The alcoholic solution precipitated with water gave 1.2 g. of an oil which on distillation was found to be tetrahydroanacardol. The two substances gave a mixed melting point of $40\text{--}44^{\circ}$ (Found : C, 80.9; H, 11.0. $\text{C}_{43}\text{H}_{70}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 81.4; H, 11.0 per cent).

Saponification of substance melting at 49° .—The substance (0.4 g.) was refluxed on the water-bath with 5 c.c. of 20% alcoholic potash for 4 hours, the alcohol evaporated off, the residue taken up with water and acidified. The product was dissolved in very dilute ammonia (100 c.c.), warmed for some time, cooled and filtered through a wet filter paper. The filtrate on acidification gave an acid (0.16 g.) which was crystallised and identified as tetrahydroanacardic acid. The product in the filter paper was shaken with 100 c.c. of ether, then twice with very dilute ammonia, the ether dried and evaporated off and the residue (0.11 g.) crystallised from petroleum ether. The resulting crystals were found to be tetrahydroanacardol.

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